

EXPLORING MARINE BIOACTIVES FOR THE TREATMENT OF POST INFLAMMATORY HYPERPIGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) causes dark skin patches after inflammation or injury and can strongly impact self-confidence, especially in darker skin tones. Conventional treatments often cause irritation or give inconsistent results. Marine-derived compounds from seaweeds and other marine organisms offer a promising natural alternative. These bioactives help reduce excess pigmentation by inhibiting melanin production, calming inflammation, and protecting the skin from oxidative damage. With improved delivery systems enhancing their effectiveness, marine bio-actives show strong potential as safe and sustainable options for PIH treatment.

KEYWORDS: Marine bio-actives, Skin depigmentation, Melanogenesis, Tyrosinase inhibition, Phlorotannins, Fucoidan, Antioxidant activity, Anti-inflammatory activity.

INTRODUCTION

1.1] What is PIH?

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation is a common acquired disorder that occurs following skin inflammation or injury. The condition is chronic and is more common and severe in individuals with darker skin tones, especially those with Fitzpatrick skin types III to VI, due to increased melanin production or irregular melanin deposition in response to skin inflammation or injury. Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation results from overproduction and irregular dispersion of melanin in the epidermis or dermis, triggered by various skin

insults, such as acne, eczema, trauma, or dermatologic procedures. The intensity and duration of pigmentation vary, influenced by factors such as the depth of melanin deposition and the individual's skin type.^[5-7]

Figure 1(a)

Figure 1(b)

Figure 1(a) and (b): Post Inflammatory Hyperpigmentation.

1.2] Etiology of PIH

While any inflammatory skin condition can cause hyperpigmentation, the most common triggers of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) in individuals with darker skin tones are acne vulgaris, atopic dermatitis, and impetigo.^[5-8] Additional causes include:

- Infections
 - Viral exanthems
 - Fungal infections
 - Impetigo

- Allergic/immunologic causes
 - Contact dermatitis
 - Atopic dermatitis
 - Systemic sclerosis (scleroderma)
 - Sarcoidosis
 - Systemic lupus erythematosus
 - Dermatomyositis
 - Insect bite reactions

- Papulosquamous disorders
 - Psoriasis

- Lichen planus
- Pityriasis rosea
- Lichen simplex chronicus

- Cutaneous injuries
 - Laser/light therapy
 - Burns
 - Cryotherapy
 - Chemical peels
 - Radiation therapy

- Miscellaneous conditions
 - Medication hypersensitivity reactions
 - Acne vulgaris
 - Mycosis fungoides
 - Erythema dyschromicum perstans

1.3] Epidemiology of PIH

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) is more commonly seen in individuals with darker skin, especially those with Fitzpatrick skin types IV to VI. This is due to higher baseline melanin levels and more responsive melanocytes. PIH is particularly frequent in people of African, Asian, and Latin American descent, where it is a common reason for dermatology visits and often develops after conditions like acne or eczema. The darker the skin, the more noticeable and long-lasting the pigmentation tends to be. In patients with darker skin who have acne, the occurrence of PIH can be as high as 65%. There is no significant difference in PIH prevalence between males and females.^[8-10]

1.4] Pathogenesis of PIH

The development of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) involves complex interactions between inflammatory signals, melanocytes, and keratinocytes. Inflammatory skin conditions- such as acne, eczema, trauma, or dermatologic procedures-trigger the release of cytokines, prostaglandins, and reactive oxygen species. These substances stimulate melanocytes to produce excess melanin, which is then transferred to nearby keratinocytes in the epidermis. In some cases, melanin may also leak into the dermis.^[11]

Epidermal PIH occurs when melanin accumulates in the upper layers of the skin and typically appears as brown discoloration. This form usually fades gradually over time. Dermal PIH, which is often associated with more severe or prolonged inflammation, results from melanin being taken up by dermal macrophages. This leads to a blue-gray discoloration that tends to be more persistent. The severity and duration of PIH depend on both the intensity of the inflammation and how deeply the melanin is deposited. Individuals with darker skin are more prone to PIH due to their higher melanin levels and increased melanocyte activity.^[5,12]

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) arises due to increased melanin production or abnormal distribution of pigment following skin inflammation. In cases where PIH is limited to the epidermis, melanocytes are stimulated to produce and transfer excess melanin to neighbouring keratinocytes. Although the exact pathways are not fully understood, various inflammatory mediators—including prostaglandins (E2, D2), leukotrienes (LT-C4, LT-D4), thromboxane A2, interleukins (IL-1, IL-6), tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), epidermal growth factor, and reactive oxygen species such as nitric oxide—have been shown to enhance melanocyte activity and melanin synthesis. In dermal PIH, inflammation leads to damage of basal keratinocytes, causing the release of melanin into the dermis. This free melanin is subsequently phagocytosed by dermal macrophages, forming melanophages. The presence of melanin deeper in the skin gives rise to a blue-gray discoloration, which is often more persistent and resistant to treatment compared to epidermal pigmentation.^[13,19]

1.5] History and Physical Examination of PIH

Patients with post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) often have a preceding history of an inflammatory skin disorder or cutaneous injury localized to the affected area. Following resolution of the primary inflammatory process, PIH is clinically asymptomatic; however, it may contribute to considerable psychological distress and diminished quality of life. On physical examination, PIH typically presents as irregularly shaped hyperpigmented macules or patches corresponding to the distribution of the prior inflammation or trauma. Epidermal PIH appears in shades of tan, brown, or dark brown. While it may persist for extended periods, spontaneous gradual improvement is common as the underlying condition resolves. Under Wood's lamp examination, epidermal hyperpigmentation may exhibit fluorescence, aiding in its differentiation from dermal involvement. Dermal PIH presents as blue-gray pigmentation and is often more persistent or permanent due to melanin deposition within the dermis. In some cases, both epidermal and dermal components may coexist. If the

inflammatory process remains active, clinical signs such as erythematous papules, plaques, or nodules may also be observed.^[5,20]

CURRENT TREATMENT APPROACHES FOR PIH

The management of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) focuses on reducing excess melanin production, accelerating pigment clearance, and preventing recurrence. Current strategies include topical depigmenting agents, procedural interventions, and strict photoprotection. The choice of treatment depends on the depth of pigmentation (epidermal or dermal), skin phototype, and underlying cause of inflammation.

1] Topical Therapy

Tyrosinase inhibitors play a central role in the management of hyperpigmentation by suppressing melanin production. The primary topical agent used is hydroquinone, which remains the gold standard due to its well-established efficacy. For patients requiring a less irritating alternative, mequinol may be considered. It is often used in combination with a topical retinoid, with or without a corticosteroid, to enhance efficacy and accelerate pigment reduction. A commonly utilized fixed-dose combination includes hydroquinone 4%, tretinoin 0.05%, and fluocinolone acetonide 0.01%. This triple combination therapy has demonstrated superior effectiveness compared to monotherapy or dual combinations. The corticosteroid component serves to mitigate irritation caused by hydroquinone and tretinoin; however, its use should be limited to no longer than 8 weeks to minimize the risk of corticosteroid-induced adverse effects, such as skin atrophy, telangiectasia, and rebound hyperpigmentation. Topical retinoids, including tretinoin, adapalene, and tazarotene, are also effective in addressing both acne and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH). Beyond their role in combination therapy, retinoids contribute to epidermal turnover, enhance penetration of other active agents, and can be safely used for long-term maintenance.^[18,19]

Azelaic acid (15–20%) possesses both anti-tyrosinase and anti-inflammatory properties and is particularly useful for acne-related PIH. Retinoids such as tretinoin and adapalene promote epidermal turnover, facilitate melanin dispersion, and enhance penetration of other depigmenting agents. Other topical agents-kojic acid, arbutin, niacinamide, vitamin C, licorice extract, and cysteamine-also show promising depigmenting and antioxidant effects with fewer side effects than HQ.^[21-23]

Tranexamic acid (TXA), applied topically or taken orally, reduces melanocyte activation by inhibiting plasmin and inflammatory mediators. It has demonstrated efficacy in both melasma and PIH, especially in darker skin types. Strict photoprotection is critical: broad-spectrum sunscreens with UVA, UVB, and visible light filters-especially tinted formulations containing iron oxides-help prevent recurrence and enhance the efficacy of all other treatments.^[24,25]

2] Chemical Peels

Chemical peels work by removing the epidermal cells containing excess melanin. Experienced clinicians should use these peels with caution as they can cause skin irritation and additional hyperpigmentation. Commonly used peels include glycolic acid, salicylic acid, and trichloroacetic acid.^[26,27]

3] Laser Therapy

Multiple laser types, including Q-switched ruby lasers, Q-switched Nd: YAG lasers, and picosecond lasers (short, intense pulse), have been used to treat post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation as fractional photo-thermolysis. However, experienced clinicians should use them cautiously, as they can cause skin irritation and additional hyperpigmentation.^[8,28]

4] Procedural Therapies

When topical therapy is insufficient, procedural options are introduced. Chemical peels, such as glycolic acid (20–70%), salicylic acid (20–30%), or trichloroacetic acid (TCA, 10–25%), accelerate exfoliation of pigmented keratinocytes and stimulate skin renewal. Microneedling improves penetration of topical depigmenting agents and promotes collagen re-modelling. Laser and light-based therapies, including low-fluence Q-switched Nd: YAG laser and fractional non-ablative lasers, target melanin granules and improve dermal pigmentation; however, improper parameters can trigger rebound PIH, especially in darker phototypes.^[29-31]

5] Recent Advances

Recent advancements in research show that topical stabilized cysteamine can be used to treat post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. This option is now considered one of the most potent options available for managing hyperpigmentation disorders in humans.

“While synthetic agents such as hydroquinone, retinoids, and corticosteroids are effective in treating PIH, their use is often limited by potential side effects. Common adverse effects include skin irritation, erythema, dryness, and, with prolonged use, risks such as exogenous

ochronosis (in hydroquinone use) or skin atrophy (with topical steroids). These concerns, along with increasing demand for safer, long-term treatment options, have fueled interest in natural and marine-derived compounds. Ingredients such as kojic acid, arbutin, licorice extract, niacinamide, and algal or marine peptides have demonstrated depigmenting effects with a more favourable safety profile. Although often less potent than synthetic agents, these alternatives are generally better tolerated and are being increasingly studied for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and tyrosinase-inhibiting properties.»^[32]

MARINE BIO-ACTIVES: AN OVERVIEW

Marine-derived pharmaceuticals have gained significant attention in the cosmeceutical industry due to their unique and diverse bioactive compounds. These substances exhibit a wide range of beneficial properties, including anti-melanogenic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-tyrosinase, and wound-healing effects, making them promising candidates for treating various dermatological conditions, including PIH.

Marine cosmeceuticals can target specific cellular pathways involved in skin aging, pigmentation, and inflammation. Compared to terrestrial plants, marine organisms can be cultivated more efficiently and consistently using modern aquaculture techniques, producing bioactive molecules with distinct chemical profiles. As consumer demand for natural, safe, and effective skincare solutions grows, marine-derived ingredients-available in formulations such as creams, lotions, and ointments-are becoming increasingly popular. These include compounds rich in vitamins, minerals, enzymes, and phytochemicals that support healthy skin, hair, and nails at the cellular level.

The wide use of different algal species in topical formulations reflects their rich biochemical diversity, with each offering unique properties that address various skin concerns. Most algae used in skincare products belong to three main groups: brown algae (Phaeophyceae), green algae (Chlorophyceae), and red algae (Rhodophyceae). This section highlights key species from each group, focusing on the specific compounds they contain and their benefits for skin health.

1] Phaeophyceae (Brown Algae) as Sources of Bioactive Compounds

Laminaria, a well-known brown algae genus, is rich in iodine, alginic acid, laminarin, potassium, and other bioactives. Extracts from species like *L. ochroleuca*, *L. cloustoni*, and *L. digitata* offer photoprotective benefits and enhance cellular metabolism. *Fucus vesiculosus* is

the most commonly used species in cosmetics, followed by *F. spiralis* and *F. serratus*, valued for their high content of iodine, zinc, magnesium, vitamin C, and bioactives like fucoidans, phlorotannins, and fucoxanthin, particularly for photoprotection. *Pylaiella* species (e.g., *P. littoralis*, *P. ochotensis*) from cold marine regions are also used for their moisturizing, antioxidant, and skin-renewing properties, due to compounds such as alginic acid, mannitol, laminarin, fucoidan, and vitamins.^[33]

Table: Examples of cosmetic ingredients obtained from brown algae.

Name/Description	Function
Fucoidan (Sulfated polysaccharide)	Antioxidant, Skin conditioning
Fucoxanthin (Carotenoid from <i>Sargassum siliquastrum</i>)	Skin conditioning
<i>Sargassum serratifolium</i> extract	Antioxidant
<i>Sargassum glaucescens</i> extract	Antioxidant
<i>Sargassum thunbergii</i> extract	Antimicrobial

2] Chlorophyceae (Green Algae) as Sources of Bioactive Compounds

Species from the *Ulva* genus are among the most widely used green macroalgae in the cosmetic industry. They exhibit two distinct morphological forms: a blistered thallus in mature specimens and a corrugated thallus in juvenile forms. *Ulva lactuca* is the most commonly utilized species, known for its rich content of vitamins A, B, C, and E, as well as minerals such as magnesium and iron. Notably, it contains a protein with an amino acid profile similar to human elastin (including glycine, proline, and lysine)- which is beneficial in anti-aging formulations aimed at reducing wrinkles and improving skin Firmness.^[33]

Table 2: Examples of cosmetic ingredients obtained from green algae.

Name/Description	Function
<i>Cladophora wrightiana</i> extract	Skin conditioning
<i>Ulva australis</i> extract	Skin conditioning-emollient
<i>Ulva rigida</i> extract	Skin conditioning
<i>Ulva linza</i> extract	Skin conditioning-emollient
<i>Ulva lactuca</i> extract	Skin conditioning, Skin protecting

3] Rhodophyceae (Red Algae) as Sources of Bioactive Compounds

The phylum *Rhodophyta*, comprising over 6,000 species with diverse morphologies, has gained attention in cosmetics for its bioactive properties. Species from the *Ceramium* genus, particularly *C. rubrum* and *C. kondoi*, are rich in amino acids, proteins, vitamins, mineral salts, and agar. These extracts are used as humectants, emollients, and skin-conditioning agents, with additional antimicrobial activity. *Polysiphonia* species also show promise due to

their strong antioxidant activity, supporting their use in anti-aging skincare formulations.^[33,35,36]

Table 3: Examples of cosmetic ingredients obtained from red algae.

Name/Description	Function
<i>Ceramium kondoi</i> extract	Humectant, Skin conditioning
<i>Polysiphonia morrowii</i> extract	Antioxidant
<i>Polysiphonia lanosa</i> extract	Skin conditioning

In conclusion, green, brown, and red algae are valuable sources of bioactive compounds with a wide range of applications in skin health, which will be further explored in the following sections. Each algal group offers specific benefits, including moisturizing, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial effects, which justify their growing use in modern topical formulations adapted to various dermatological needs.

Classification of Macroalgal Bio-actives

Algae-derived compounds are of significant interest due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, and anti-aging properties, making them valuable in both cosmetics and wound care. These bio-actives include polysaccharides, pigments (chlorophylls, carotenoids), and mycosporine-like amino acids (MAAs). These compounds are widely used in skincare products as moisturizers, anti-wrinkle agents, sunscreens, and texture enhancers.^[37]

1] Polysaccharides: Polysaccharides are large, water-soluble carbohydrates composed of long chains of monosaccharide units connected by glycosidic bonds. Polysaccharides are the most notable compounds found in algae, each type of seaweed being correlated with a specific qualitative and quantitative profile of these macromolecules: alginate, laminarin and fucoidan being predominant in Phaeophyta, agar and carrageenan in Rhodophyta, and ulvan in Chlorophyta.^[37]

1.1] Alginates

Alginates are abundant in brown algae (*Phaeophyta*) species such as *Ascophyllum*, *Durvillaea*, *Ecklonia*, *Laminaria*, *Lessonia*, *Macrocystis*, *Saccharina*, *Sargassum*, and *Turbinaria*. These are anionic polysaccharides made up mainly of two types of uronic acids: β -D-mannuronic acid and α -L-guluronic acid. Alginates are valued in cosmetics for their anti-

allergic and antimicrobial properties, as well as their film-forming, thickening (rheological), and skin-conditioning effects.^[37]

1.2] Laminarin

Laminarin is a polysaccharide mainly found in brown algae, especially in species from the Laminariaceae family. Key sources include *Laminaria digitata*, *L. japonica*, *Eisenia bicyclis*, *Saccharina latissima*, and *Ecklonia kurome*, with smaller amounts found in *Fucus*, *Ascophyllum*, and *Undaria*. Laminarin has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, and studies have also shown its potential anti-tumor effects. When broken down by irradiation, its ability to neutralize free radicals and reduce melanin production in melanoma cells is further enhanced.^[38]

1.3] Fucoidans

Fucoidans are sulfated polysaccharides mainly made up of fucose, along with other sugars like xylose, galactose, mannose, and glucuronic acid. They also contain sulfate groups, uronic acids, and acetyl groups. Fucoidans are known for their strong antioxidant activity, which depends on their molecular weight and sulfate content. In skincare, they help prevent and treat photoaging by inhibiting UVB-induced enzymes such as collagenase, gelatinase, and elastase. They also support collagen production in human skin cells, reduce inflammation, and protect the skin's extracellular matrix by blocking matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), enzymes linked to wrinkle formation.^[39]

1.4] Ulvan

Ulvan is a major sulfated polysaccharide found in green algae, making up 8% to 29% of their dry weight. It is mainly composed of rhamnose, xylose, glucose, glucuronic acid, iduronic acid, and sulfate. In the presence of divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+}), ulvan forms gels at pH 7.5–8.0 and remains stable up to 180 °C. Its gelling and anti-aging properties make it valuable in cosmeceutical formulations. Additionally, ulvan has shown anti-hyper lipidemic and antiherpetic activities.^[39]

1.5] Agar

Agar is a gelatinous hydrocolloid extracted from various red algae and is composed mainly of two carbohydrates: agarose and agarpectin. Agarose, which makes up 50–90% of agar, provides its strong gelling properties. Agar remains stable at high temperatures, up to 250 °C, making it ideal for cosmetic use. It is widely used as a thickening, emulsifying, and

stabilizing agent in products such as moisturizers, creams, cleansers, liquid soaps, and deodorants—especially in formulations targeting anti-aging and acne treatment.^[39-40]

1.6] Carrageenan

Carrageenan is a polysaccharide found in red algae, particularly in species of the order *Gigartinales*, also known as carrageenophytes. In its natural form, carrageenin is unstable, but when combined with cations, it forms stable carrageenan salts. Carrageenan occurs in three main types: kappa (κ), iota (ι), and lambda (λ). Kappa and iota form gels, while lambda functions mainly as a thickening agent. Due to these properties, carrageenan is commonly used in cosmetics as a natural alternative to synthetic thickeners like polyethylene glycol (PEG) and carbomer.^[39,41]

2] Proteins, Peptides and Amino Acids: Amino acids play a vital role in maintaining skin hydration as part of the natural moisturizing factor (NMF). All macroalgae contain both essential and non-essential amino acids, with red algae having the highest protein content (up to 47%), followed by green (9–26%) and brown algae (3–15%). Seaweed-derived proteins and low-molecular-weight peptides exhibit strong antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Species like *Palmaria* and *Porphyra* are rich in arginine, a NMF component. Red algae also contain bioactive peptides such as carnosine, glutathione, taurine, and PPY1, which offer antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and collagen-boosting benefits.^[38,41]

2.1] Mycosporine-like Amino Acids

MAAs are small, UV-absorbing molecules (<400 Da) found in the cytoplasm of algae. Their structure includes a cyclohexenone or cyclohexenimine ring linked to amino acid residues, enabling broad UV absorption. These compounds are highly relevant for sunscreen formulations due to their natural photoprotective properties, which vary based on their substituent groups.^[39,42]

3] Phenolic Compounds: Phenolic compounds are water-soluble molecules with hydroxyl groups attached to aromatic rings, ranging from 126 to 65,000 Da in size. They are secondary metabolites produced as defense against environmental stress. These include simple phenolics and polyphenols such as terpenoids, flavonoids, phlorotannins, and bromophenols. Brown algae are rich in phlorotannins, while green and red algae mainly contain bromophenols, flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, and MAAs. This composition distinguishes algal polyphenols from those of terrestrial plants.^[43]

3.1] Phlorotannins

Phlorotannins are a key class of polyphenols found mainly in brown algae, constituting 5–12% of their dry weight. They are polymers of phloroglucinol with a 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene structure and are classified into six types: phloroethols, fuhalols, fucophloroethols, fucols, eckols, and carmalols. Phlorotannins inhibit tyrosinase, show antidiabetic activity, and possess strong antioxidant, anti-allergic, and anti-inflammatory effects, making them valuable in cosmetics. Studies also demonstrate their UV-protective properties and their ability to reduce MMP-1 expression, helping prevent collagen breakdown and skin aging.^[44,45]

3.2] Phenolic Terpenoids

Phenolic terpenoids, a diverse group of natural compounds, are found in both brown and red algae. Red algae mainly contain diterpenes and sesquiterpenes, while brown algae are rich in meroditerpenoids—compounds with a hydroquinone core and polyprenyl side chain, including plastoquinones, chromanols, and chromenes. Meroditerpenoids are recognized for strong antioxidant activity, photoaging inhibition, and a favorable safety profile. They effectively reduce UVA-induced skin damage and photodamage, making them valuable in dermatological and cosmetic products. Some also exhibit skin-lightening effects, enhancing their multifunctional cosmetic use.^[39]

4] Lipids: Seaweeds have low lipid content (<5%), rich in beneficial polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) like α -linolenic, arachidonic, and eicosapentaenoic acids. Linoleic acid is vital for maintaining skin's water barrier. Seaweed lipids also include sterols such as fucosterol, which enhance antioxidant defenses and protect against UV-induced skin damage. Certain fatty acids and essential oils from species like *Gracilaria verrucosa* and *Laminaria ochroleuca* exhibit anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, hydrating, and antioxidant effects. These bioactive lipids contribute to the skin benefits and cosmeceutical potential of seaweed extracts.^[40,45,46]

5] Vitamins and Minerals: Algae are rich in vitamins (A, B-complex, C, E, K) and minerals (zinc, magnesium, iodine), essential for skin health. They provide antioxidants, boost hydration, support barrier function, and aid repair. Primary compounds like polysaccharides and lipids hydrate and regenerate skin, while secondary metabolites offer anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, and photoprotective benefits. Their diverse bioactive profile makes algae valuable, natural, and sustainable ingredients in modern cosmeceuticals.

6] Pigments

6.1] Carotenoids: Carotenoids, including carotenes (α -, β -carotene, lycopene) and xanthophylls (lutein, astaxanthin, fucoxanthin), offer strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer benefits. They protect against photooxidative stress and support skin and eye health. Astaxanthin is valued in cosmetics for its potent free radical scavenging and vibrant color, while fucoxanthin, dominant in brown algae, shows diverse therapeutic effects including anti-obesity and anti-inflammatory properties.

Table 4: Classification of Marine Bio-actives for PIH Treatment.

Class	Example	Source Organism	Mechanism in PIH
Polyphenols	Phlorotannins (e.g., dieckol, eckol)	Brown algae (<i>Ecklonia cava</i>)	Tyrosinase inhibition, antioxidant
Polysaccharides	Fucoidan	Brown algae (<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>)	Anti-inflammatory, inhibits cytokine pathways
Carotenoids	Astaxanthin	Microalgae (<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>)	Antioxidant, reduces oxidative stress
Peptides	Marine collagen peptides	Fish skin/scales, jellyfish	Promotes healing, reduces inflammation
MAAs	Shinorine, Palythine	Red algae (<i>Porphyra spp.</i>)	UV absorption, antioxidant
Terpenes/Alkaloids	Triterpene glycosides	Sea cucumber (<i>Stichopus japonicus</i>)	Tyrosinase inhibition, anti-inflammatory

EXTRACTION & CHARACTERIZATION OF MARINE BIO-ACTIVES FOR PIH

1. Extraction Methods of Bioactive Compounds from Macroalgae

Extraction is a crucial step in obtaining bioactive compounds from algae. After algae are collected, the biomass is processed based on the target bioactive compounds. The first step usually involves drying the biomass—either through low-temperature oven drying (below 40 °C) to preserve sensitive compounds like proteins and vitamins, or by lyophilization (freeze-drying). Once dried, the biomass is ground to a fine powder for direct cosmetic use or further extraction. To isolate specific active ingredients for cosmetic or pharmaceutical applications, various extraction methods are used. These fall into two categories:

- Classical methods: maceration, percolation, Soxhlet extraction, and both solid–liquid and liquid–liquid extraction.
- Modern methods: microwave-assisted, ultrasound-assisted, enzyme-assisted extraction, as well as supercritical fluid and pressurized liquid extraction.

Modern techniques follow green chemistry principles-aiming to reduce energy use, solvent consumption, and environmental impact, while improving efficiency and purity.^[39,47]

1.1. Classical Extraction Methods

1.1.1. Maceration: Maceration is a traditional extraction method used for macroalgae. It involves soaking dried or fresh, ground algae in solvents like methanol, ethanol, or water at room temperature or slightly above, typically for 24 to 72 hours. This gentle process allows the solvent to penetrate algal cells and extract valuable compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, pigments, and other secondary metabolites. Antioxidants and pigments are commonly obtained using this method. The effectiveness of extraction depends on factors such as the type of solvent used, extraction duration, and the specific algal species.^[48,49]

1.1.2. Percolation: Percolation is a dynamic extraction method where a solvent continuously flows through a column packed with macroalgal material. This allows for more efficient extraction and larger extract volumes compared to maceration. The efficiency of the process depends on the type of solvent and extraction conditions. For example, Baliano *et al.* used this method with methanol to produce bioactive extracts from *Padina gymnospora*, which showed potential for wound-healing applications.^[50]

1.1.3. Soxhlet extraction: Soxhlet extraction is a continuous solvent-based method used to selectively extract target compounds from solid materials at room pressure and boiling temperature. Compared to maceration and percolation, it is faster and uses less solvent. This method offers several advantages: it eliminates the need for filtration, allows simultaneous processing of multiple samples, and enables solvent recycling. However, the use of higher temperatures and longer extraction times can increase the risk of thermal degradation of sensitive compounds. Bhuyar *et al.* applied Soxhlet extraction to red seaweed *Kappaphycus alvarezii*, finding that the ethanolic extract had a slightly higher phenolic content (20.25 ± 0.03 mg GAE/g DW) compared to the hot water extract (19.10 ± 0.81 mg GAE/g DW), supporting its antioxidant and antibacterial potential.^[51,52]

1.1.4. Hot-Water Extraction: Hot-water extraction is one of the most effective and widely used methods for extracting bioactive compounds from algae, especially polysaccharides. Water is a safe, non-toxic solvent that easily penetrates plant tissues, making this method both practical and efficient. Although extraction yields can vary depending on factors like time,

temperature, and the algae-to-water ratio, the resulting extracts often show strong biological activities such as antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and hypolipidemic effects. Due to its simplicity, low cost, and ability to preserve sensitive compounds, hot-water extraction remains a preferred method for producing marine polysaccharide extracts used in food, medicine, and cosmetics.^[53,54]

1.2. Modern Extraction Method

1.2.1. Microwave-Assisted Extraction: Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) is an advanced and efficient technique used to extract valuable bioactive compounds from macroalgae. It uses microwave energy to rapidly heat the solvent and algal biomass, breaking down cell walls and releasing compounds such as sodium alginate, phenolics, phlorotannins, polysaccharides, and carotenoids. Compared to traditional methods, MAE significantly reduces extraction time- often to just minutes- while achieving higher yields and greater total phenolic content. For example, extractions performed at 110 °C for 15 minutes have shown improved antioxidant and enzyme-inhibiting activities. MAE is a fast, eco-friendly, and high-yield method that offers clear advantages over conventional techniques in terms of efficiency, extract quality, and environmental sustainability.^[55-60]

1.2.2. Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE): Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is a modern and efficient technique that uses ultrasonic waves to break down algal cell walls, enhancing the release of key bioactive compounds such as phenolics, polysaccharides, pigments, and proteins. Compared to traditional methods, UAE significantly increases the yield and antioxidant activity of compounds like tannins, phenols, phlorotannins, flavonoids, fucoxanthin, phycobiliproteins, and amino acids. Its efficiency can be further improved by combining it with other techniques like homogenization or maceration. UAE is considered environmentally friendly due to its lower energy and solvent requirements. It is a fast, scalable, and sustainable method widely applicable in the food, cosmetic, and nutraceutical industries.^[61-68]

1.2.3. Enzyme-Assisted Extraction (EAE): Enzyme-assisted extraction (EAE) is a gentle and innovative method that uses specific enzymes to break down algal cell walls and release valuable compounds such as polysaccharides and proteins. EAE is especially effective for extracting ulvan from green macroalgae and high-molecular-weight fucoidans from brown macroalgae, often yielding more intact and bioactive molecules compared to traditional chemical methods. Key factors like pH, temperature, and extraction time must be optimized

for the best results. Enzyme selection—such as cellulases, alginate lyases, or proteases—can be tailored to the algal species and the target compound. EAE can also be combined with techniques like ultrasound or pulsed electric fields to boost yields and antioxidant activity. Overall, EAE is a sustainable, efficient, and selective method suitable for producing high-quality bioactive compounds for use in food, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and other biotechnological applications.^[69-75]

1.2.4. Pressurized Liquid Extraction (PLE): Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) is a green and efficient technique that uses high temperatures and pressures to extract bioactive compounds from macroalgae, including fatty acids, polyphenols, carotenoids, and phycobiliproteins. By adjusting solvents (e.g., ethanol, water, acetone, ethyl acetate) and extraction conditions, PLE allows for selective extraction of specific compounds. For example, ethanol–water mixtures are effective for extracting polyphenols and flavonoids with strong antioxidant and antimicrobial activity, while ethyl acetate at high temperatures targets long-chain fatty acids like oleic, arachidonic, and eicosapentaenoic acids. Extraction efficiency is influenced by factors such as the drying method (oven vs. freeze-drying), solvent type, temperature, pressure, and solvent ratios. Under optimized conditions, yields of compounds like carotenoids and tocopherols can increase by up to six times. PLE is a fast, versatile, and environmentally friendly method, though its success depends on fine-tuning parameters for each macroalgal species and target compound.^[71,76-79]

1.2.5. Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE): Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE), typically using supercritical CO₂, is an environmentally friendly and efficient method for extracting high-value bioactive compounds from macroalgae. These include fatty acids, phenolics, flavonoids, and pigments like carotenoids and chlorophylls. SFE operates under high pressure and moderate temperatures, enabling selective extraction without toxic solvents. This helps preserve the structure and bioactivity of sensitive compounds. Extracts obtained via SFE have demonstrated strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties, making them suitable for use in food, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and agricultural bio-stimulants. Additionally, SFE produces stable, consistent extracts ideal for industrial applications. While highly effective, the efficiency of SFE depends on the macroalgal species and compound polarity. In some cases, other methods like ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) may be more suitable for specific compounds such as certain polyphenols.^[80-84]

Marine bio-actives, including phlorotannins, fucoidan, carotenoids, and marine peptides, must undergo efficient extraction and characterization to ensure their purity, stability, and bioactivity. These techniques are critical in isolating compounds with anti-melanogenic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, which are directly applicable to managing post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH).

Table 5: Extraction Techniques of Marine Bio-actives.

Method	Application
Solvent Extraction	Phlorotannins, carotenoids (e.g., methanol, ethanol)
Enzyme-Assisted Extraction (EAE)	Fucoidan, marine peptides
Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE)	MAAs, antioxidants
Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE)	Astaxanthin (CO ₂ -based)
Pressurized Liquid Extraction (PLE)	Polyphenols, antioxidants

Table 6: Characterization Techniques of Marine Bio-actives.

Technique	Purpose
UV-Vis, HPLC, MS	Quantification & purity of compounds (e.g., astaxanthin, phlorotannins)
FTIR, NMR	Functional groups & structural identification
Chromatography (HPLC, Ion-exchange)	Purification of fucoidan, peptides

ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF SKIN

The skin, also referred to as the integumentary system, represents the largest organ of the human body, encompassing the entire external surface. In an average adult, it covers an area of approximately 2m² and accounts for about 4.5–5 kg, or roughly 12–15% of total body weight. Functioning as the primary physical barrier, the skin provides essential protection against environmental factors. Structurally, it is composed of three distinct layers: the outermost epidermis, the underlying dermis, and the deeper subcutaneous tissue. Each of these layers exhibits unique anatomical, structural, and compositional characteristics that correspond to its specific physiological roles and functions.^[85-87]

Figure 3: Anatomy of Skin.

Figure 4: Microscopic anatomy of skin.

1] Epidermis

The epidermis varies in thickness from approximately 0.5 mm on the eyelids to 1.5 mm on the palms and soles. It is an avascular, keratinized, stratified squamous epithelium. Based on thickness, the skin is categorized as thick skin (palms, soles, and fingerprints) and thin skin (all other areas). Thin skin comprises four distinct layers—stratum basale (germinativum), stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum, and stratum corneum—whereas thick skin contains an additional layer, the stratum lucidum, between the stratum granulosum and stratum corneum. The epidermis primarily consists of keratinocytes and melanocytes, with fewer Langerhans and Merkel cells.^[88-91]

1.1] Stratum corneum: The stratum corneum is the outermost and thickest layer of the epidermis, comprising approximately 25–30 layers of large, flattened, anucleate keratinocytes. These cells are densely packed with keratin and structural proteins, forming a rigid, impermeable barrier. The surface pH ranges from 4.0 to 6.5, and alterations in this acidity can predispose the skin to bacterial or fungal infections. This layer undergoes continuous renewal, with complete turnover occurring approximately every four weeks. In aged skin, keratinocyte turnover decreases, and the migration time from the basal layer to the surface may increase by up to 50%, accompanied by a thickening of the stratum corneum—a response believed to enhance protection against cumulative UV exposure.^[85,88,92-94]

1.2] Stratum lucidum: The stratum lucidum comprises two to three layers of transparent keratinocytes and is present only in thick skin—such as the palms, soles, and fingerprints. Its

clear appearance results from the densely packed, transparent nature of the keratinocytes within this layer.^[86]

1.3] Stratum granulosum (granular layer): The stratum granulosum consists of three to five layers of flattened granular cells that differentiate from the underlying spinous layer. These cells contain two main types of granules: keratohyalin granules, which hold keratin precursors that aggregate and cross-link to form keratin bundles, and lamellar granules, which are rich in glycolipids that function as intercellular cement, contributing to the skin's hydrophobic barrier.² The diamond-shaped cells in this layer lie parallel to the basement membrane and continue to mature as they migrate toward the stratum corneum, where they form the fully keratinized surface cells.^[86]

1.4] Stratum spinosum (prickle/spinous layer): The stratum spinosum, located directly above the basal layer, consists of 8–10 layers of polyhedral keratinocytes interconnected by desmosomes, which appear as cytoplasmic “spines” under microscopy. Within this layer, keratinocytes continue to differentiate, ultimately forming the cells of the stratum corneum. Dendritic (Langerhans) cells are also present, contributing to immune surveillance. With aging, the stratum spinosum becomes progressively thinner.^[86,94,95]

1.5] Stratum basale /stratum germinativum (basal layer): The stratum basale (or stratum germinativum) forms the deepest layer of the epidermis and is composed of a single row of cuboidal basal cells, which serve as stem cells giving rise to keratinocytes. These cells are mitotically active, ensuring continuous epidermal renewal. Melanocytes, interspersed among basal cells, synthesize melanin, providing pigmentation and UV protection. This layer is anchored to the underlying dermis by the basement membrane (basal lamina) through specialized junctions known as hemidesmosomes.^[85,86,88,92,95,96]

1.6] The basement membrane: The basement membrane lies directly beneath the epidermis, forming a distinct boundary that separates and anchors the epidermis to the dermis. It is rich in extracellular matrix (ECM) components, which create an adhesive microenvironment that ensures strong dermal–epidermal cohesion. With aging, the basement membrane atrophies, leading to flattening of the dermal–epidermal junction and a decline in epidermal adhesion. These changes are attributed to alterations in the protein composition of the dermal–epidermal interface, resulting in reduced structural integrity between the two layers.^[92,94,97]

Figure 5: Anatomical structure of Epidermis.

2] Dermis

The dermis is the layer of skin located beneath the epidermis, providing structural support and nourishment to it. Its thickness varies from 0.3 mm on the eyelids to about 3.0 mm on the back. It contains fibroblasts, mast cells, and macrophages responsible for maintaining skin integrity and defence. Collagen is the principal structural protein of the dermis, contributing to its tensile strength and elasticity. Approximately 80% of dermal collagen is type I, 15% is type III, and smaller amounts are types IV and V. Elastic fibers interwoven throughout the dermis enable skin recoil, though aging and ultraviolet exposure can degrade these fibers, leading to wrinkles. The dermis is divided into two layers:

2.1] Papillary Dermis: The papillary dermis is the thin, superficial layer that connects the dermis to the epidermis. It contains finger-like projections known as rete pegs, which increase the surface area for oxygen and nutrient exchange. These structures reduce with age, leading to decreased epidermal adhesion. This layer consists of loosely arranged connective tissue rich in ground substance containing glycosaminoglycans and anionic polysaccharides. Fibroblasts and mast cells regulate collagen interaction and water balance, while the gel-like matrix aids nutrient and hormone diffusion. The papillary dermis also contains sensory nerve endings responsible for pain, touch, and temperature sensations.

2.2] Reticular Dermis: The reticular dermis lies beneath the papillary layer and extends to the subcutaneous tissue. It is thicker and composed of densely packed collagen and elastic fibres arranged parallel to the skin surface, providing tensile strength and structural support. The collagen fibres form a well-organized lattice or mesh-like network that contributes to

skin firmness and elasticity. This layer's robust collagen bundles are essential for wound healing and surgical skin closure.^[98,99]

3] Hypodermis (Subcutaneous Layer)

The hypodermis, also referred to as the subcutaneous layer or superficial fascia, lies beneath the dermis and anchors it to the underlying muscular or osseous fascia. This layer is primarily composed of adipose tissue, which serves as a reservoir for fat storage and provides cushioning and thermal insulation. In addition, the hypodermis contains well-vascularized loose areolar connective tissue, contributing to the flexibility and mobility of the skin over deeper structures due to the loose arrangement of collagen and elastic fibers. With aging, both adipose content and cushioning capacity of the hypodermis decline, reducing its protective and insulating functions.^[88,94,100]

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF MARINE COMPOUNDS

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) is caused by excessive melanin production or abnormal melanin distribution following cutaneous inflammation, trauma, or irritation. Marine bio-actives compounds derived from marine organisms such as algae, invertebrates, and microorganisms- have shown potential in managing PIH through multiple therapeutic actions:

□ 1. Inhibition of Melanogenesis

PIH is directly linked to the overactivation of melanogenesis, the process by which melanin is synthesized in melanocytes. Marine-derived polyphenols, especially phlorotannins from brown algae (*Ecklonia cava*, *Ecklonia stolonifera*), have been shown to effectively inhibit tyrosinase, the rate-limiting enzyme in melanin synthesis. These compounds also downregulate melanogenic proteins such as TRP-1, TRP-2, and MITF (microphthalmia-associated transcription factor), reducing melanin accumulation in keratinocytes.

- **Example:** Dieckol and eckol significantly decreased melanin content and tyrosinase activity in B16F10 melanoma cells.

□ 2. Anti-inflammatory Activity

Inflammation is a key trigger in PIH pathogenesis, as inflammatory mediators like IL-6, TNF- α , and prostaglandins stimulate melanocyte activity. Marine polysaccharides, particularly fucoidan, possess strong anti-inflammatory properties. Fucoidan downregulates

pro-inflammatory cytokines and inhibits NF- κ B signaling, thereby reducing the inflammatory response that drives melanogenesis.

- **Example:** Fucoidan extracted from *Fucus vesiculosus* reduced IL-6 and TNF- α levels in UVB-exposed skin models.

□ 3. Antioxidant Protection

Oxidative stress caused by UV exposure or inflammation promotes PIH by stimulating melanogenic enzymes and increasing ROS (reactive oxygen species). Marine compounds such as astaxanthin (a carotenoid from *Haematococcus pluvialis*) and mycosporine-like amino acids (MAAs) from red algae act as potent antioxidants, scavenging ROS and inhibiting oxidative damage to melanocytes.

- Astaxanthin neutralizes singlet oxygen and lipid peroxides, protecting skin cells and regulating melanin production indirectly.
- MAAs, including shinorine and porphyra-334, also absorb harmful UV radiation and protect DNA from UV-induced pigmentation.

□ 4. Skin Regeneration and Wound Healing

PIH often follows skin trauma, and faster wound healing reduces the risk and severity of pigmentation. Marine collagen peptides and bioactive peptides derived from fish skin, sea cucumbers, or jellyfish promote skin repair, collagen synthesis, and barrier restoration.

- These peptides enhance fibroblast activity, reduce matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), and suppress post-wound inflammation.
- **Example:** Oral and topical marine collagen peptides have shown clinical benefits in skin hydration, elasticity, and pigmentation reduction.

□ 5. Photoprotection

UV radiation worsens PIH by promoting melanocyte activity and oxidative damage. Marine compounds like MAAs and carotenoids offer natural UV-protective effects, reducing the chances of pigmentation worsening.

- MAAs can absorb UV rays (310–360 nm) and are stable in cosmetic formulations, making them attractive for skin-lightening products.

Examples of Marine-Derived Compounds with Anti-Hyperpigmentation Potential

Hyperpigmentation refers to the darkening of skin due to the overproduction of melanin, the pigment responsible for skin, hair, and eye colour. This process is primarily regulated by the enzyme tyrosinase, which catalyzes the conversion of tyrosine to melanin. As a result, inhibitors of tyrosinase are often used as depigmenting or skin-lightening agents.

Marine environments are rich in bioactive compounds due to their biodiversity and extreme ecological conditions, leading to the evolution of unique secondary metabolites. Marine organisms such as algae, sponges, fungi, bacteria, and invertebrates have become promising sources of natural compounds with anti-melanogenic or anti-hyperpigmentation effects.

Marine-derived anti-hyperpigmentation agents typically work through one or more of the following mechanisms:

1. **Tyrosinase inhibition** – direct or via chelation
2. **Downregulation of melanogenic genes** (e.g., MITF, TYR, TRP-1, TRP-2)
3. **UV protection** – reducing UV-induced melanogenesis
4. **Antioxidant activity** – preventing oxidative stress that triggers melanin production
5. **Anti-inflammatory effects** – reducing skin irritation that may lead to pigmentation

Marine-Derived Compounds with Anti-Hyperpigmentation Activity

1. Phlorotannins

- Source: Brown seaweeds (e.g., *Ecklonia cava*, *Ishige okamurae*)
- Mechanism of Action: Inhibit tyrosinase activity and melanin synthesis by chelating copper ions in the enzyme's active site.
- Additional Effects: Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
- Example: Dieckol – a potent phlorotannin that suppresses melanin production in melanocytes.

2. Fucoidan

- Source: Brown algae (e.g., *Fucus vesiculosus*, *Undaria pinnatifida*)
- Mechanism of Action: Inhibits melanogenesis via downregulation of MITF (Microphthalmia-associated transcription factor), a key regulator of melanin production.
- Additional Effects: Anti-aging, moisturizing, and anti-inflammatory properties.

3. Mycosporine-like Amino Acids (MAAs)

- Source: Cyanobacteria, red algae, marine fungi
- Mechanism of Action: Absorb UV radiation and reduce UV-induced melanin production by preventing oxidative stress.
- Additional Effects: Natural UV filters, antioxidant.

4. Marine Sponge-Derived Compounds

- Source: Marine sponges (e.g., *Haliclona*, *Ircinia*)
- Compound: Fascaplysin – has shown inhibitory effects on melanin synthesis.
- Mechanism: May involve tyrosinase inhibition or downstream signaling interference in melanogenesis.

5. Astaxanthin

- Source: Microalgae (*Haematococcus pluvialis*) and marine animals (krill, shrimp)
- Mechanism of Action: Potent antioxidant that reduces oxidative stress-induced melanogenesis; may modulate melanogenic genes.
- Note: Astaxanthin is also known for improving skin elasticity and photoprotection.

6. Marine-Derived Peptides

- Source: Marine bacteria, fish, and algae
- Mechanism of Action: Some peptides can modulate signaling pathways (e.g., cAMP/PKA, MAPK) involved in melanogenesis.
- Example: Peptides from fish skin hydrolysates have shown tyrosinase inhibition in vitro.

7. Sargaquinoic Acid and Sargachromenol

- Source: *Sargassum serratifolium* (brown algae)
- Mechanism of Action: Inhibit tyrosinase activity and downregulate MITF expression in melanocytes.^[106]

Table 7: Important antimicrobial activities of marine compounds reported in the literature.

Marine Compound	Source	Mode of Action	Findings
Zinc oxide	Zincite, resource, a mineral can be used to create natural zinc oxide. Further more, it is synthesized.	Antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects can be obtained by zinc oxide. It reduces sebum production, prevents the development of germs that cause acne (such Propionibacterium acnes), and reduces inflammation brought on by acne lesions.	It has a little dehydrating effect that aids in absorbing extra oil and clearing pores.
Alginate	Produced by a number of different brown seaweed species, including Laminaria and Ascophyllum.	It helps to absorb excess oil from the skin and regulates sebum production. Additionally, it has anti-inflammatory properties that reduce acne-related redness and inflammation.	Alginate helps gently exfoliate dead cells from the skin, which can help with skin cleanliness.
Niacinamide	Vitamin B3 comes in the form of niacinamide, which can be produced artificially or obtained naturally from foods like fish	It reduces inflammation, regulates sebum production, and strengthens the skin's protective barrier.	Niacinamide also aids in the reduction of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH), a condition frequently associated with acne, and has anti-bacterial properties against germs that cause acne.
Sea whip extract	Produced by Pseudopterogorgia elisabethae, a type of Caribbean gorgonian coral.	It has calming and anti-inflammatory properties. It reduces redness and soothes inflammation brought on by acne.	Promotes a healthy complexion by reducing excessive sebum production.
Chitosan	Obtained from crustacean shells, such as those of crabs, prawns and lobsters.	Antimicrobial and wound healing capabilities are both found in chitosan. It aids in reducing acne-related inflammation and preventing acne causing bacteria from growing.	Chitosan promotes skin regeneration and can speed up the recovery of acne lesions.
Fucoidan	Brown seaweeds like Sargassum and Fucus vesiculosus.	It has anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial effects Both inflammation and the development of acne-causing bacteria are inhibited.	Fucoidan supports a healthy skin barrier and regulates sebum production.
Marine peptides	Produced by a variety of marine creatures, including	Marine peptides have antibacterial qualities that	Marine peptides have the ability to improve skin

	sponges, fish, and algae.	work to kill acne-causing bacteria and reduce acne inflammation. Additionally, they can speed up wound healing and minimize acne scarring.	moisture and improve general skin health.
Marine enzymes	Obtained from marine sources, such as papaya (papain) & pineapple (bromelain).	They aid in unclogging pores, removing dead skin cells, and reducing acne-related irritation.	These enzymes may be helpful to reduce acne-related PIH.

EVALUATION OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF ALGAE THROUGH IN VITRO AND IN VIVO STUDIES

Marine algal extracts support skin health through multiple mechanisms, including the inhibition of melanin production, reduction of oxidative stress, anti-inflammatory activity, UV protection, and anti-aging effects.

Table 8: Main active ingredients from algae and their skin health benefits.

Active Ingredients from Algae	Beneficial Effects in Skin Health
Phlorotannins, carotenoids, photolyase, mycosporine-like amino acids	UV-protection
Tocopherols, polyphenols, β -carotenoids (vitamin A), other carotenoids	Skin protection (radical scavenging and immune system stimulation)
(Sulfated) polysaccharides, glycosaminoglycans	Skin moisturizing
Essential and nonproteinogenic amino acids, highly unsaturated fatty acids	Skin smoothing and regeneration
Phlorotannins, phloroglucinol and its oligomers	Skin whitening
Low-molecular-weight fucoidans	Stimulation of collagen synthesis

Table 9: Bioactive extracts from specific algae species and their in vitro/in vivo demonstrated effects.

Active Ingredients from Algae	Beneficial Effects in Skin Health
Alginates (<i>Sargassum vulgare</i>)	Increase antimicrobial properties
Brown algae polysaccharides (<i>Hizikia fusiforme</i>)	UVB protection (protection collagen synthesis and \downarrow MMPs expression in UVB-irradiated human dermal fibroblasts)
Fucoidans (<i>Sargassum tenerrimum</i> , <i>Laminaria japonica</i> , <i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>)	Antioxidant activity (superoxide radical scavenging properties)
Fucoidans (<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>)	Anti-aging, UV protection, wrinkle reduction, antioxidant, collagen synthesis
Phlorotannins from <i>Cystoseira nodicaulis</i> , <i>Cystoseira tamariscifolia</i> , <i>Cystoseira usneoides</i> <i>Fucus spiralis</i>	Hyaluronidase inhibition, antioxidant activity (superoxide radical scavenging properties, lipid peroxidation inhibition)
<i>Pyropia yezoensis</i> extract	Increase collagen synthesis, prevents its degradation (human skin fibroblasts) Decrease

	melanin content (inhibits tyrosinase activity)
Laminarin	UVB protection (Decrease ROS production and Increase endogenous antioxidant levels against UVB irradiation)

Table 10: Summary of clinical studies on macroalgae-derived cosmetic formulations.

Algae Species (Type)	Formulation	Study Design (Subjects, Duration)	Outcomes	Effect
Fucus vesiculosus+ Ulva lactuca (brown+ green) + ectoin	Serum mist (split-face)	28days, 33adults	+17% hydration; pH normalized	Hydration/ wrinkle reduction
Fucus vesiculosus (brown)	Cream (1%)	5weeks, 10women	↑elasticity, 7–8%↓ skin thickness	Firming/ anti-aging
Fucus vesiculosus (brown, fucoidan/ polyphenols)	Gel (0.3%)	60days, 30subjects	↑brightness, ↓wrinkles, ↓age spots	Brightening/ anti-aging
Ascophyllum nodosum (brown) + herbal extract	Botanical regiment	18 weeks, 56 women; 1 year extension	Comparable to hydroquinone/ tretinoin; no rebound pigmentation	Anti pigmentation
Porphyra umbilicalis (red, MAAs)	Cream (0.005%) vs.sunscreen	4weeks, 20women	UVA protection; ↑ firmness, ↑ smoothness	Photoprotection/ anti-aging

FORMULATION STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES FOR ALGAL EXTRACTS IN TOPICAL PRODUCTS

Formulation Strategies

To enhance the stability, bioavailability, and performance of algal bioactive compounds in skincare products, various advanced formulation strategies are employed:

- Encapsulation is the most effective approach, protecting sensitive compounds and improving their controlled release and skin penetration.
- Emulsion-based systems (e.g., creams, nano emulsions, and multiple emulsions) are widely used, particularly for hydrophilic and lipophilic algae-derived ingredients.
- Vesicular carriers such as liposomes, niosomes, and transfersomes enhance the delivery and bioactivity of compounds like polyphenols and carotenoids.
- Particulate systems (e.g., nano- and microparticles, cyclodextrin complexes) help stabilize and incorporate unstable ingredients into cosmetic formulations.

Formulation Challenges

- Low chemical stability of key compounds like polyphenols and carotenoids, which are sensitive to oxygen, light, temperature, and storage conditions.

- Lack of regulatory guidelines for maximum permissible concentrations and safety evaluation of algal ingredients in cosmetics.
- Variability in extract composition due to differences in algae species, growth conditions, and extraction methods.
- Scalability and sustainability of formulation technologies, which must align with eco-friendly practices for industrial production.^[108-113]

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Despite the growing interest in marine-based products, the number of commercially available marine-derived cosmeceuticals remains limited relative to the vast potential of oceanic biodiversity. As of 2012, only three categories of marine algal compounds-agar, carrageenan, and alginates-had been widely commercialized. This highlights the untapped potential of numerous marine-derived compounds, particularly low molecular weight bio-actives, for cosmeceutical applications.

However, significant efforts are still required in the isolation, characterization, and identification of active pharmacophores, as well as in understanding their molecular modifications, pharmacological activities, and safety profiles. Advancing these areas will be essential to improve product efficacy and safety. Furthermore, increased investment in research and development is critical to fully unlock the potential of marine algae in cosmetic and therapeutic formulations.^[106]

CONCLUSION

The growing global desire to maintain a youthful and healthy appearance particularly among the aging baby boomer generation has driven increased interest in natural and sustainable cosmetic solutions. Public awareness of the potential risks associated with synthetic chemicals in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals has risen significantly, aided by social media and the rapid dissemination of scientific information. As a result, the current era is increasingly defined by the use of natural ingredients and eco-friendly practices.

Marine biotechnology, also known as blue biotechnology, is emerging as a promising alternative to traditional green technology, offering a diverse array of bioactive compounds with unique biological and pharmacological properties not typically found in terrestrial sources. While the pharmaceutical industry has traditionally led the exploration of marine-

derived compounds, the cosmetic sector is now placing greater emphasis on marine ecosystems.

Despite their vast potential, marine resources remain underutilized due to key challenges. These include the limited number of bioactive molecules isolated from marine organisms and the variability in compound production caused by environmental fluctuations. To overcome these limitations, sustainable approaches such as controlled cultivation of marine organisms under optimal conditions are essential. This strategy could enhance the viability of marine biotechnology as a reliable source of high-value compounds for cosmeceutical applications.

SUMMARY

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) is a common skin condition that appears as dark patches after inflammation or injury and can significantly affect confidence, especially in people with darker skin tones. Although treatments like hydroquinone, retinoids, and chemical peels are widely used, they often cause irritation, uneven results, or long-term side effects. Because of these limitations, there is growing interest in safer and more natural treatment options.

Marine organisms such as algae and other sea-derived sources contain unique bioactive compounds, including phlorotannins, fucoidan, carotenoids, mycosporine-like amino acids, and marine peptides, which show promising benefits for PIH management. These compounds help reduce excess pigmentation by slowing down melanin production, calming inflammation, protecting the skin from oxidative damage, and shielding it from harmful UV rays. Recent improvements in extraction and formulation technologies have also made these marine ingredients more stable and effective when applied to the skin.

Overall, this review highlights the strong potential of marine bio-actives as gentle, sustainable, and multi-functional alternatives for treating post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. While further clinical studies are needed, marine-based compounds offer an encouraging future for safer and more effective skin-lightening and repair formulations.

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